

ISic3908

I.Sicily inscription 3908

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic (pietra di Fuardo)

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Exact provenance unknown; seen by Libertini (1921) in villa Di Mauro,
contr. Diana

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, Museo Archeologico

Regionale Eoliano "Luigi Bernabò Brea", inventory 903

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI334366

1. Παρμένοντος.

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

PHI 334366

Bibliography

Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M., Campagna, L. 2003. Meligunìs Lipára. XII. Le

iscrizioni lapidarie greche e latine delle isole eolie. Palermo. At 264
Libertini, G 1921. Le isole eolie nell'antichità greca e romana. Ricerche storiche
ed archeologiche. Florence. At 225 no.47

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3908. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI
edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4389339>